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DETERMINATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF RESERVOIR FLUIDS AND GASES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MULTI-LAYER DEPOSITS BY DUAL COMPLETION

Deryaev A.R.

*Candidate of Technical Sciences, Senior Researcher,
Scientific Research Institute of Natural Gas
of the State Concern „Turkmengas”,
Ashgabat, Turkmenistan*

Abstract

The article is devoted to determining the properties of reservoir fluids and gases, as well as performing calculations to determine the dependence of the volume of dissolved gas in oil, the volume coefficient of dynamic viscosity and density on saturation pressure, determining the compressibility coefficient and other necessary indicators for the development of the multi-layer Altuguyi field by dual completion (DC)

This work can be used to determine the heterogeneity of oil and gas in productive horizons for the development of multi-layer deposits by the DC method.

Keywords: volume coefficient, compressibility coefficient, gas-saturated oil, dynamic viscosity, reservoir oil, hydrocarbon fluid, reservoir pressure.

The analytical dependence of the volume of dissolved gas in oil, the volume coefficient of dynamic viscosity and density on the saturation pressure is given in the following form [1, 2]:

$$G = 0,3652 \times P_{\text{sat.}} + 10,265 \quad (1)$$

$$b = 1,0839 + 0,0008982 \cdot P_{\text{sat.}}; \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = 6,92526 \cdot \exp^{-0,0045489 \cdot P_{\text{sat.}}}; \quad (3)$$

$$\rho = 0,000000522 \cdot P_{\text{sat.}}^2 - 0,00053 \cdot P_{\text{sat.}} + 0,8645; \quad (4)$$

here :

$P_{\text{sat.}}$ -saturation pressure, kgf/cm²;

G is the volume of dissolved gas m³/m³;

b is the volume coefficient of oil;

μ is the dynamic viscosity, sp;

ρ is the density of reservoir oil, g/cm².

To determine the value of the initial volume coefficient at the initial reservoir pressure, the following dependence is used:

$$b_{\text{init.}} = b \cdot \left[1 - \beta \cdot (P_{\text{res.pres.}} - P_{\text{sat.}}) \right] \quad (5)$$

here:

b- at saturation pressure;

$P_{\text{sat.}}$ - volume coefficient of gas-saturated oil;

β is the compressibility coefficient of reservoir oil.

To determine the compressibility coefficient given in this work using a graph of the relationship between saturation pressure and the density of reservoir oil, polynomial interpolations are constructed [3].

$$\beta = (8,16562 \cdot \rho^2 - 20,35479 \cdot \rho + 12,12085) \cdot 10^{-4}; \quad (6)$$

here:

ρ -density of reservoir oil, g/cm²

The dynamic viscosity at reservoir pressure of carbonated oil is determined by the formula obtained from the dependence of the Bill graph:

$$\mu_{\text{res}} = \mu_{\text{res.sat.}} + \sigma \cdot (P_{\text{res}} - P_{\text{sat.}}); \quad (7)$$

here:

μ_{res} - viscosity of oil with dissolved gas at reservoir pressure and reservoir temperature, sP;

$\mu_{res.sat}$ - viscosity of gas-saturated oil at reservoir pressure and reservoir temperature, sP;

$P_{res}-P_{sat}$ - reservoir pressure and saturation pressure, kg/cm²

σ - the coefficient of approximation of the dependence of the equation of the Beale graph.

The initial values of the reservoir oil of the wells of the NK₉ horizon of the Altyguyi field are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

The result of the analysis of recombined (artificial) oil samples

Well number	Degree of degassing	Saturation pressure (kgf/cm ²)	Volume of dissolved gas in reservoir oil (m ³ /m ³)	Volume coefficient of oil (b)
2	P_{res}	480	-	-
	P_{sat}	374,5	157,8	1,433
	I	350	148	1,406
	II	300	127,4	1,351
	III	250	107	1,296
	IV	200	86,5	1,241
	V	150	66,1	1,186
	VI	100	45,6	1,130
3		50	25,2	1,075
	P_{res}	408	-	1,418
	P_{sat}	342	150,7	1,435
	I	288	118,8	1,387
	II	216	89,4	1,360
	III	144	60,8	1,256
	IV	72	35	1,100
		360	15,5	1,060
4	P_{res}	504	-	1,367
	P_{sat}	408	148,0	1,384
	I	336	125,5	1,360
	II	240	107,0	1,312
	III	144	75,3	1,269
	IV	48	45,3	1,210
		12,0	13,9	1,040
7	P_{res}	408	-	1,260
	P_{sat}	326,4	96,5	1,320
	I	240,0	77,3	1,300
	II	168,0	60,0	1,270
	III	84,0	37,1	1,230
10	P_{res}	338,4	137,7	1,380
1	P_{sat}	367,0	149,0	1,406

Table 2

The result of the analysis of recombined (artificial) oil samples

Well number	Dynamic viscosity of oil, sP	Oil density g/cm ³		Gas density g/l
		in formation conditions	in atmospheric conditions	
2	-	-	-	-
	1,261	0,729	0,9024	0,730
	1,357	0,737		
	1,600	0,753		
	1,879	0,771		
	2,245	0,790		
	2,773	0,811		
	3,622	0,835		
5,028	0,861			
3	1,745	-	-	-
	1,623	0,734	0,9100	0,565
	2,107	-	-	-
	2,737	0,768	-	-
	3,760	0,856	0,9035	0,569
	5,550	0,862		
	8,200	-		
1,290	-			
4	1,163	0,745	0,916	-
	1,590	0,746		
	2,096	0,762		
	2,975	0,767		
	4,999	0,780		
	6,900	0,881		
7	2,240	-	-	-
	2,126	0,760	0,916	-
	2,763	-	0,8982	-
	3,798	0,764		
	5,612	0,772		
10	1,356	0,749	0,9121	-
1	1,176	0,737	0,9121	-

The initial value of the main physical indicators of the oil horizon NK₉ Altyguyi field:

- Initial volume of dissolved gas in reservoir oil -148.6 m³/m³;
- The initial volume coefficient of gas-saturated oil is 1.408;
- The initial coefficient of dynamic viscosity of gas-saturated oil is 1.316 sp.

The composition and properties of hydrocarbon fluids are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5.

Table 3

Initial values of reservoir oil indicators of the NK₉ horizon

Well number	Initial saturation pressures kg/cm ²	Initial volume of dissolved gas in reservoir oil m ³ /m ³	Initial volume coefficient of gas-saturated oil	Initial coefficient of dynamic viscosity of gas-saturated oil, sP
1	367	149	1,406	1,176
2	374,5	157,8	1,433	1,261
3	342	150,7	1,435	1,623
4	408	148	1,384	1,163
7	326,4	96,5	1,320	2,126
10	338,4	137,7	1,380	1,356

Table 4

Properties and composition of oil and condensate (horizontal average)

Horizon	Perforation interval (m)	D ²⁰ ₄	T _{sol} C ⁰	Viscosity, sPz	
				20 C ⁰	50 C ⁰
oil					
NK-9	3670-3680	0,9103	+36	non - fluid	63,8
condensate					
NK -7d	3512-3624	0,7943	-3	1,9	-
NK -8	3616-3625	0,7903	+3	1,8	-

Table 5

Properties and composition of oil and condensate (horizontal average)

Horizon	Perforation interval (m)	End of boiling %, up to temperature C ⁰					
		100	150	200	250	300	exit
oil							
NK -9	3670-3680	-	4	7	10	16	-
condensate							
NK -7d	3512-3624	12	29	42	56	74	90
NK -8	3616-3625	9	27	42	57	76	93

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NEUTRAL GROUNDING MODE IN THE 6–35 kV NETWORK THROUGH AN ARCING REACTOR AND ORGANIZATION OF RELAY PROTECTION AGAINST SINGLE-PHASE GROUND FAULTS

Rzayeva S.V.

Head of laboratory, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Mammadov N.S.

Chief laborant, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Ganiyeva N.A.

Chief laborant, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

The choice of the neutral grounding mode in the 6–35 kV network (or, in other words, the method of neutral grounding) is an extremely important issue in the design and operation. In this article, one of the neutral grounding modes in 6-35kV networks is considered - through an arcing reactor. The choice of the neutral grounding mode in 6–35 kV networks is an extremely important issue in the operation and design of the network.

The use of modern neutral grounding equipment in 6–35 kV networks (arc-quenching reactors with low-voltage shunt resistors and high-voltage neutral grounding resistors) can significantly improve the reliability of networks, automate the search for a damaged feeder and reduce accidents in case of single-phase ground faults.

Keywords: neutral grounding, arcing reactor, shunt resistor, arc surges

The neutral grounding mode in the 6–35 kV network determines:

- current in the place of damage and overvoltage on undamaged phases in case of single-phase circuit;
- scheme for constructing relay protection against earth faults;

- electrical equipment insulation level;
- uninterrupted power supply;
- allowable resistance of the substation ground loop;
- safety of personnel and electrical equipment during single-phase faults.